

Music in Beckett

A short assessment of the musical qualities of Samuel Beckett's *Rockaby*.

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Musical qualities can be roughly gleaned from any art. The most farfetched, perhaps, being sculpture or painting, but as we get closer, theatre seems to confront music (which I will define here as an artistic arrangement of sounds for listening pleasure and discourse) directly and strides the boundary between text, sound and music.

Music is not a close cousin to theatre, musical performance is evident in even the earliest accounts of theatre, from Greek antiquity to Indian Sanskrit theatre, where music was a live part in the action on stage and a play between the musicians and actors was fundamental to the dramatic content and plot. A further similarity is apparent in the two states that music and theatre occupy, the first being the written document, the fundamental work without which a performance would not be possible.

Both of their sources are born on the manuscript and it is up to the interpreting musician or actor to make it into reality; the second stage, which is the vision of the writer or composer.

However, through this, the work changes from being a stationary, timeless art into being a living, temporal art and thus is critically vulnerable and subject to much discussion. The interpreter's freedom is only limited by specifics outlined in the score (apart from stylistic convention or affiliation), their performance ability and then only their imagination. Countless transformations can exist from text to performance and many times a performance can be heard/seen a hundred times and still seem fresh and new.

In this essay I will endeavour to draw the lines of theatre and music closer on the textual level and analyse works based on musical principals of variation and development of material. To this end I will complete a short analysis of Samuel Beckett's *Rockaby* (written in 1980 in English and first performed in 1981) which was written during his late 'minimalist' period. I will also relate these findings to common transferable trends in art during the twentieth century.

The works of Samuel Beckett present to me many musical features which I will outline through the course of this essay. Many musicians have sought the works of Samuel Beckett for inspiration, either by an overall fascination of the style and a wish to depict musically a certain piece of his work, or, by direct quotation and use of dramatic material pertaining to a certain work, either performed by a speaker or vocalist in the work or by the use of rhythmic features of the text as a melodic construction. In the Oxford university press' book published in 2001 titled 'Music and Beckett', the editor mentions several art music works in which the work of Samuel Beckett was a direct inspiration. Composers as early as 1968, just before Beckett won the Nobel prize for literature, started utilising his literary material (for example the use of fragments from his novel *The Unnameable* in a work titled 'Sinfonia'(1968) by the Italian composer Luciano Berio (b. 24/10/1925, d. 27/6/2003).

I will now show a list of other composers who have used Beckett as inspiration for their works.

Csapó, Gyula; *Krapp's Last Tape* -- after Samuel Beckett (1975),

Feldman, Morton; *Neither* (1977), *Words and Music* (1987), *For Samuel Beckett* (1987).

Glass, Philip; *Company* (1983). Also music for *Play*, *The Lost Ones*, *Cascando*, *Mercier and Camier*, and *Worstward Ho*.

Marsh, Roger; *PS* (1971), *Bits & Scraps* (1979).

Reynolds, Roger; *Ping* (1968), *Odyssey* (1976), *Voicespace II*, "*A Merciful Coincidence*" (1993).

Amirkhanian, Charles; *Pas de Voix (Portrait of Samuel Beckett)* (1987).

Barrett, Richard; *Nothing Elsewhere* (1987), *I Open and Close* (1988), *Another Heavenly Day* (1990) and *How It Is*.

Duncan, John & Bernhard Gunter; *Unspeakable House*.

Gudmundsen-Holmgreen, Pelle; *Je ne me Tarais Jamais, Jamais* (1966), *Trois poemes de Samuel*

Beckett (1989), *Songs Without* (1976).

Kim, Earl; *Exercises en Route* (1961-1970), *...dead calm...* (1961), *They Are Far Out* (1966), *Gooseberries*, *She Said* (1967), *...rattling on...* (1970), *Footfalls* (1981), *Narratives: Seven Pieces Based on Texts by Beckett* (1973-1976), *Now and Then* (1981).

Kurtág, György; *Samuel Beckett Sends Word Through Ildikó Monyók in the Translation of István Sik* (1990), *Samuel Beckett: What is the World* (1990), *... pas à pas - nulle part...* (1997).

Miller, Mark E.; *Words and Music* (1979).

Phillips, John J. H.; *The things one has to listen to...* (1990).

These works, along with newer works such as *'re:play'* (2007) by Irish composer Ian Wilson (b.1964), show a great wealth and respect for the influence of Beckett both at home and abroad. Wilson's piece; written for improvising tenor sax, piano, string quartet and bass uses melodic and rhythmic material inspired by the play *'Play'*, which turns out to be a kind of listening and memory recall of the work under the impression of the composer. It is changed so much that scarcely a word of the original text can be identified by the listener. And perhaps a closer look at the score could yield more tangible results.

Before I look specifically at Beckett's work I will give a small background on the post-modernist genre of Minimalism in both literature and music, to give an idea of how closely the two arts can relate. Minimalism in music is usually seen as the stronger in the two arts with more definite stylised characteristics. Minimalism was created more or less as a direct reaction to the modernist tendencies in music at the beginning of the twentieth century where composers were using increased methods of complicated expression, to combat this; minimalist composers (mainly American) of the late twentieth century utilised a reductive approach of material. Melody, harmony, instrumentation, rhythm and the concept of time were stripped down and re-arranged as never before. A kind of back to basics approach was used where it seemed like they were re-assessing

western art music from a new beginning. The main composers from the American school of minimalism were and still are;

John Adams (b. 1947), Philip Glass (b.1937), Steve Reich (b.1936) and Terry Riley (b.1935).

Minimalism in literature also features a paring down of material and an attention to abstract detail in where the reader is given considerable space to interpret the work, specifics are avoided and only the bare, most important details of the work's concept are apparent in the piece.

Reading such works often poses problems to some less experienced readers, and with such little text the work is often quite quick to read through, but hard to grasp immediately. Careful attention to detail is often required to appreciate the meaning of the work and to get an accurate impression of what the writer was trying to convey.

Assessing Beckett's *Rockaby* (1980) for musical material.

This text, written for a female actor and an unseen commentator of the same voice, split into four verses spoken by the voice (v.) and at the end of each verse a duet of voice and the woman (w.) then followed by the word 'More.' spoken solely by the w., constitutes the main bulk of the play, apart from the stage directions. The first verse utilises abstract prose and when heard at first, scarcely makes any sense. But as the second and third verses are heard, a picture gradually emerges as to the predicament of the speaker and gives the reader clues as to her ultimate fate. Beckett adds words periodically to fill in the missing gaps in the text. This technique of not disclosing the theme too quickly, leading to a materialisation of the story towards the end, is quite common in contemporary western art music. Where musical fragments of the essential theme of the work are given in random formation in order to perplex (or indeed test) the listener. This technique which followed on from the technique of developing variation from previous eras can be quite effective and eventually can lead to a strong unity at the end of a piece. This teasing out the theme forces the audience to pay more attention to the work in order to discover, and perhaps reveal, its meaning. This I feel promotes more discourse on the work. To return to *Rockaby*: V. uses quite a lot of repetition, for example the

word 'Day' is repeated; 4 times in the first verse, 3 times in the second, 5 times in the third and 5 times in the fourth verse. Also, throughout the stage directions there is evidence of descriptive musicality in the tone of the voice which decreases in immediacy throughout the fourth verse, working as a kind of degradation in volume or decrescendo. The rhythm of this text is fairly steady and is complimented by the mechanical rock of the chair, changing only for a brief pause between the verses when the w. has to respond to the speaker in order to continue rocking. The performer is given considerable space to interpret this work when recording the v. part and the sense of timing here is crucial to the ease of the w. part, which would have to be listened to frequently (or even memorised) in order to continue at the right moment and to dictate the length of the pause which is needed between verses.

All these aspects I feel give a definite musicality to the play and highlights a certain sensitivity to sound and silence which are definitely evident in Rockaby.

Although I believe that the two art forms of Theatre and Music can be very closely related, it is clear that they were from generated from very different beginnings and indeed endeavour to serve different purposes of expression. I feel that in some situations they can be drawn together by comparison, but in others can seem utterly different; whereas text must convey meaning or it would seem useless, music on the other hand can just convey sound and sound for sound's sake. Thus, a certain importance can be given to literature in its communicative importance. Needless to say, they have different uses and ends, but I believe whether consciously or subconsciously, that Samuel Beckett was influenced in some way by music, something which is quite hard not to be ignore these days.

Not only this, but that the influence of music and musical expression is evident in his work.

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